

PRECONCEPTION PREPARATION FOR WOMEN WITH POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME

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Relevance. Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a common hormonal disorder that occurs in women of reproductive age. PCOS usually begins in adolescence, but symptoms may change over time. In recent decades, due to global urbanization and a decrease in physical activity, there has been an active increase in the number of people with overweight and obesity around the world, which makes this problem one of the most pressing for the medical community. Weight gain is associated with many associated diseases, including metabolic and cardiovascular disorders.

Keywords. PCOS (Polycystic ovary syndrome), Obesity, reproductive disorders, Hyperinsulinemia

Purpose. PCOS can cause hormonal imbalances, irregular menstrual cycles, excessive androgen levels, and the formation of cysts in the ovaries. An irregular menstrual cycle, usually accompanied by a lack of ovulation, can make it difficult to get pregnant. PCOS is the leading cause of infertility.

Materials and methods. The mechanism of development of infertility in such patients includes deregulation of the gonadotropic axis, changes in the follicular apparatus of the ovaries with the formation of PCOS and impaired endometrial receptivity. These defects are mediated by increased IR, subsequent compensatory hyperinsulinemia, decreased adiponectin concentrations, increased androgen production, and increased levels of leptin, interleukin (IL) 6, and tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α). Due to significant clinical heterogeneity, giving rise to a number of phenotypes with or without weight loss, the difference and variability of clinical signs that change throughout life, as well as the systemic effect on the body, infertility treatment in PCOS, despite active study in the last decade, seems a pressing issue that deserves close attention. The complex pathophysiology and clinical heterogeneity of PCOS do not facilitate a clear understanding of the interactions between PCOS, excess body weight, and body fat distribution. Obesity with visceral distribution of adipose tissue increases IR and compensatory hyperinsulinemia. Due to the interaction between IR and the gonadotropic, luteinizing hormone-stimulating action of insulin, an increase in the level of circulating androgens occurs. Hyperinsulinemia plays an important role in the pathogenesis of PCOS, causing a decrease in serum sex steroid binding globulin, which leads to an increase in free and metabolically active androgens in the serum, a decrease in androgen clearance and aromatase activity, and increased steroidogenesis. This aggravates the clinical manifestations of PCOS and accelerates its manifestation, so it is often difficult to say what became the primary pathology: a disorder of fat metabolism or PCOS. Obesity affects the phenotypic expression of PCOS, exacerbating metabolic, reproductive and psychological disorders.

Results. PCOS is a significant public health problem and one of the most common hormonal disorders among women of reproductive age. The syndrome is estimated to occur in 8–13% of women of reproductive age, with up to 70% of cases remaining undiagnosed. The prevalence of PCOS is higher in some ethnic groups, whose representatives may be more

likely to experience complications of the syndrome, in particular metabolic disorders. The physical and psychological consequences of PCOS, especially those related to obesity, body image and infertility, can lead to mental health problems and social stigma. The incidence of overweight or obesity is higher in women with PCOS compared to the general population, which may be due to a genetic predisposition to obesity in these patients. If the prevalence of MS in the general population is 14–24%, then among patients with PCOS it reaches 43%. In women with a BMI > 25 kg/m², the diagnosis of PCOS is 9% more common. Once diagnosed with PCOS, the incidence of obesity increases in the future. Abdominal obesity increases over time with a progressive increase in waist-to-hip ratio between 20–25 and 40–45 years of age.

Conclusion. WHO is working with Member States to address PCOS as part of its efforts to improve the health and reproductive well-being of women worldwide. In collaboration with government and non-government partners, the Organization raises awareness of PCOS and provides health care providers with guidance on how to identify and treat the syndrome. In addition, WHO promotes research to develop the most effective methods for preventing, diagnosing and treating infertility caused by PCOS, and identifies the most pressing unresolved issues in this area.

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